

Table 2. E values for five functions.

Function	PR109			PR106		
	Plants	Tillers	Grains	Plants	Tillers	Grains
$y = mx + c$	0.041	0.085	0.156	0.035	0.039	0.051
$e^y = ax^b$	0.185	0.201	0.054	0.163	0.082	0.063
$y = ab^x$	0.052	0.050	0.202	0.071	0.081	0.087
$y = ax^b$	0.097	0.110	0.056	0.073	0.030	0.018
$y = ax^2 + bx + c$	0.027	0.060	0.065	0.035	0.002	0.006

was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Five levels of N were the main plots and cultivars the subplots.

Soil had 29 kg available N/ha, 1.2 kg available P/ha, and 45 kg available K/ha. To compensate for P deficiency and to maintain N levels of 29, 92, 154, 217, and 279 kg/ha, 25 kg P/ha and one-third of the N were applied before puddling. The remaining N was applied equally at 3 and 6 wk after transplanting.

We randomly selected three 1-m² areas in each plot at crop maturity and recorded disease incidence. Percentage of infected plants, tillers, and grains in both cultivars were calculated (Table 1).

Five equations (exponentials: $e^y = ax^b$, $y = ab^x$, $y = ax^b$, and polynomials) were used to describe the relationship between nitrogen (x) and disease incidence (y). Functions were fit to data using standard error or estimate: $E = [(1/N)\sum\{(fp - fo)/$

$fo\}^2]^{1/2}$, where fp (predicted) and fo (observed) are data from N measurements.

E was used to compare regression models (Table 2). A threshold of E = 0.1, which corresponds to an average error of 10% between observed and predicted data, was chosen for selecting the relationship. The best fit was obtained with a quadratic function with error variance of 0.02-0.07.

A quadratic function ($y = ax^2 + bx + c$) was used to predict disease (Table 1). Residuals (9%) were located randomly on both sides of the predicted curve.

For this data set, a quadratic model best described the relationship between N level and false smut intensity. This type of regression model could be used to predict disease incidence provided other conditions match closely. Planners can use these predictions to estimate crop losses. ■

A rapid method for screening rice-associated bacteria antagonistic to *Rhizoctonia solani*

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Screening isolates is an important step in developing biological control agents for *R. solani*, the causal agent of sheath blight (ShB) of rice. We developed a rapid and simple method for screening large numbers of isolates for antagonism to *R. solani*.

Bacterial isolates were isolated and tested for antagonistic effect on *R. solani* by dual culture on potato sucrose agar medium. We used 208 bacterial isolates that strongly inhibited in vitro *R. solani* mycelium growth to determine the effect of seed bacterization. Seeds of mungbean (another host of *R. solani*) and *R. solani* inoculum were spread on sterilized petri dishes. Bacterial suspension was sprayed on each dish. Dishes were kept in a growth chamber.

Damping-off incidence, assessed as percent diseased mungbean plants, was measured 5 d after inoculation. Eighteen of the 288 antagonistic isolates tested reduced damping-off incidence to 50% of that of the control and were considered effective.

The ability of these 18 isolates to protect rice leaves from *R. solani* infection and to restrict lesion expansion was verified with the detached-leaf technique (Rosales et al 1993). Antagonism to infection was tested by spraying rice leaves with bacterial suspension and then placing mycelia discs of *R. solani* on each leaf. Inhibition of lesion expansion was tested by infecting rice leaves with *R. solani* and then spraying bacterial suspension on leaves. We conducted the two experiments in randomized complete block design. Each treatment was replicated three times. Inoculated leaves were incubated in moist chambers at 28-30°C. Lesion length was measured 5 d after applying the bacteria.

Ten of the 18 isolates protected rice leaves from infection, and 11 inhibited ability to inhibit lesion expansion (see table). Further evaluation is needed if

isolates obtained through this rapid screening method reflect biological control ability in the field. Our next step is to test selected isolates in the greenhouse and field to confirm their effectiveness as biological control agents. ■

Lesion length of rice ShB in detached leaf test. Guangzhou, China, 1991.

Bacterial isolate	Lesion length (mm) ^a	
	Antagonism to infection	Inhibition of lesion extension
12542	0 a	1.3 a
Rh71	0 a	2.5 a
RH72	1.7 a	41.0 c
Jinggangmycin ^b	2.3 a	4.2 ab
RH62	4.3 a	2.7 a
11541	7.5 a	24.1 bc
RH921	9.7 a	9.5 ab
RH715	11.7 a	6.0 ab
RH121	15.8 a	8.5 ab
RH22	16.5 a	0.5 a
RH92	17.2 a	6.8 ab
RH131	43.2 b	4.3 ab
9642	45.7 bc	11.0 ab
RH76	51.8 bc	9.2 ab
Check	57.7 bc	30.7 c
8343	67.2 c	39.8 c

^aResults reported are based on two experiments where each treatment was replicated three times. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bAntibiotic made in China.